

Master thesis on Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Exploring Robust Music Fingerprinting Methods With Data-driven Methodologies

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Supervisor: Marius Mirion

Co-Supervisor: Furkan Yesiler

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Abstract

Music recognition tools have been one of the primary research problems in music information retrieval. Recent advancements in neural networks have shown that unsupervised and semi-supervised learning frameworks can be used to learn latent embeddings of musical data which, in turn, can be used as compact and unique fingerprints for query search and retrieval. These frameworks are data-driven, scalable to real-world applications, and robust to noisy environments and transformations which may, advertently or inadvertently, make its way into the query audio recordings in a real-world setting. This work implements a self-supervised contrastive learning architecture for audio fingerprinting which can be scalable to a large music dataset. Motivated by the domain-knowledge of music, this work also proposes modifications which would improve its performance in particularly two aspects: robustness to pitch-shifting and time-stretching.

Keywords: content-based music information retrieval, music information retrieval, audio fingerprint, self-supervised learning, audio signal processing.

Chapter 1

Introduction

Ever since there was a shift of the music distribution paradigm from store purchases to streaming and downloading via the Internet, users have felt the need for on-demand audio recognition from recorded audio segments (say, using smartphones). To meet such utility, there have been significant advances in the development of audio recognition frameworks. Any large-scale audio recognition requires some sort of content-based audio retrieval. And often search queries are noisy signals with additional spurious information superimposed with the characteristics necessary for the retrieval task. The audio recognition task is two-fold: it involves the creation of a dataset of signatures or fingerprints of music recordings and facilitating fast-search through the fingerprint dataset for real-time query response. The fast searching is accomplished through hashing methods and, more recently, neural network frameworks have been used to develop optimal hashing. This thesis aims to focus on the audio fingerprinting task and proposes a data-driven approach to deal with scalability and robustness.

1.1 Problem Definition

The problem of audio fingerprinting can be defined as a sub-problem of audio content-based identification and, at the same time, a framework which supports such an application. In order to extract acoustically relevant characteristics, an au-

audio piece can be summarised into a signature for the entire piece. This signature or audio fingerprint has to be such that an unknown audio snippets with a sufficiently similar fingerprint could be classified can be identified as the same audio. In practice, this query matching is a search problem on a large database of fingerprints. The Figure 1 illustrates the various steps involved in the audio fingerprinting process.

Figure 1: Block Diagram illustrating the general architecture of audio fingerprinting

In order to draw comparison between audio fingerprinting frameworks, it is essential to define the properties which are desirable in a fingerprinting system. For the sake of this project, the following list of properties would enable us to evaluate different methodolgies and our contribution [1]:

- **Accuracy:** This measures the degree to which the identification results are correct. In this context, as will be discussed in the later sections, specificity is a more important measure as compared to accuracy as wrong identifications (false positives) is required to be penalised to a greater extent than missed identifications.
- **Computational complexity:** It refers to the computational overhead and cost

involved in the various steps: fingerprint computation, query matching from a large fingerprint dataset and audio identification.

- **Efficiency:** This is closely related to the previous property and is important for real-time applications of audio fingerprinting.
- **Fingerprint size:** A size of a single fingerprint is an important parameter as a small increase in storage size of a single fingerprint affects the size of the reference database
- **Granularity:** [1] defines it as “the minimum length of the audio clip required for a dependable identification.” When a system is said to be fine granular, it means that the system is capable of reliable identification of audio clip by making use of small excerpts.
- **Robustness:** A fingerprint framework is required to be robust to superimposed noise, compression caused by transmitting devices. In addition to this, it should withstand the effect of transformations such as time scaling, time stretching and pitch shifting. It must be noted here that time scaling is not the same as time stretching and it refers to the change in speed due to down-sampling or up-sampling; time scaling would inadvertently cause pitch shifting as well.
- **Scalability:** The framework should be able to exhibit similar performance for a larger dataset. This especially applies to the query matching and searching process which depend on the efficient indexing or hashing of the fingerprints in the reference database.

1.2 Review of Frameworks

1.2.1 Shazam-like Fingerprinting Frameworks

As stated earlier, audio fingerprints of music recordings have to be based on the content of the waveform rather than web-based information retrieval frameworks

which rely on metadata associated with the audio files. Wang et al (2006) [2] proposed an audio fingerprinting and recognition framework which was based on the assumption that a constellation map of spectral peaks contains the relevant information necessary for creating a signature of the audio. Intuitively, this accounts for the degradation due to lossy recording of the query sound. The fingerprints are formulated by hashing each point in the constellation map to specific anchor landmarks. The hashing function links the anchor landmarks to a target zone, consisting of a consecutive time window, in the constellation map of spectral peaks. A similar landmarking procedure based on local maxima is applied to the query sound. Identification of the query sample is performed by matching the linear correspondence of spectral peaks of candidate fingerprints from the database. One of the main issues in the framework is robustness to temporal variations (especially, time-stretching) as the key assumption for identification is that the time offset of corresponding spectral peaks is invariant. The effect of time-stretching was tested on the implementation of the algorithm presented in [3]. The results are shown in Figure ??.

Figure 2: Performance of chromaprint against pitch-shifting

The problem of robustness to time is somewhat alleviated in the Panako [4] framework by encoding the ratio of time offset between triplets of anchor points into the

Figure 3: Performance of chromaprint against time-stretching

hashing. A similar encoding is performed to account for pitch-shifting as well. This proves to be more spatially expensive for the storage of fingerprints in the database. The framework uses an approach which is very similar to [2] for query search and retrieval (query matching). In addition to this, the framework uses a constant-Q transform spectrogram to improve the extraction of event points and, hence, the fingerprints.

Another similar notable improvement on the Shazam algorithm was proposed in [5] and is referred to as *Qfp*. Instead of hashing pairs of landmark locations, the implemented system stores “quads” of peak locations. This ensures invariance to isotropic as well as non-isotropic scaling; as a result the quads algorithm is very robust against transformations such as pitch shifting and time stretching. In addition to this, the *Qfp* framework includes Locality Sensitive Hashing (LSH) to index the quads in the reference database. In the experiments performed in [6], it has been observed that *Qfp* can resist upto 30% time scaling. However, the construction of the quads is a computationally intensive step. This presents a major scalability issue which is not helped by the high space complexity of storing the quads. Despite being landmark-based approach robust time variations, the *Qfp* does not perform

well against compression techniques used by mobile devices [6].

The above algorithms are based on particular assumptions derived from domain-related knowledge. And so the frameworks are unable to handle instances which are exceptional to these assumptions. For instance, both [2] and [4] do not perform well on music with spectrograms either with very little energy or energy evenly spread across the range. Also extremely repetitive music, with a spectrogram similar to a series of dirac impulses is observed to cause problems in [4].

1.2.2 Philips Fingerprint and its Variations

Departing from the landmark-based frameworks, [7] presents a system referred to as the Philips fingerprint algorithm. This algorithm relies on long spectrogram frames with a high overlapping factor (31 parts out of 32). The strategy used is to divide the Short-Term Fourier Transform features derived from an audio signal into 33 non-overlapping log-scaled frequency bands. Thus each frame consists of a series of sub-fingerprints which can be stored in 32 bits. The sub-prints are hashed into the reference database. During query matching, the bit-error rate is minimized between the sub-prints of the query and that of the candidate fingerprints in the database to give the correct identification.

While Philips fingerprint is more robust to transformations than the vanilla Shazam fingerprint, it is significantly more computationally complex and has a large fingerprint size. As is pointed out in [8], the look-up process requires computing similarity using the hamming distance between the database sub-prints and the query sub-prints. This results in 33-times more query matching time for audio identification.

The contribution of [9] combines the approach of proposed in [2] and [7] by using finding peak locations inside constant-Q transform (CQT) bins in a series of overlapping temporal frames. In practice, each frame (0.4 second in length) gives 12 rectangular subsections and one peak is chosen in each rectangle. These sub-prints are hashed in a pairwise fashion, storing the difference between time frames and CQT bins respectively. Since, pitch become additive in the CQT domain, the

proposed algorithm is robust to pitch-shifting.

Another improvement on the Philip fingerprint framework is shown in [6], which combines the fingerprint computation proposed in the former with an audio retrieval and indexing algorithm referred to in the work as Enhanced Sampling and Counting (eSC) [10]. In this technique, a Fibonacci hashing is applied for indexing and storage. A key concept in this technique is identifying “turning points” in the sub-prints: the approximate number of most significant bits that remain unchanged between a query sub-print and a distorted version of the query sub-print. Using these turning points the query searching considerably reduces the complexity of the process.

1.2.3 Computer Vision and Audio Fingerprinting

With the advancements in the field of computer vision, a number of audio fingerprinting frameworks are borrowed the state-of-the-art. One of the main intuitions behind this is that every audio piece can be pre-processed into a spectrogram which contain its characteristic features and a spectrogram can be treated as an image. Such is the motivation of the method proposed in [11]. This framework uses Scale Invariant Feature Transform (SIFT) based descriptors to extract robust image features and hence audio features. SIFT is an object identification algorithm which causes the extracted descriptor points to be invariant to affine transformations. Hence, the computed fingerprints are robust to small pitch shifts and time stretching. It is unclear, however, if the framework is scalable for real-time application as the implementation has been done on a small reference database with an exhaustive query searching without any speed-up.

The chromaprint [12] framework is loosely based on [13] and [14]. The fingerprints in this framework is derived from chroma (PCP) features rather than spectral feature. This decision is musically motivated and using pitch class representation greatly eases the storage space required for the fingerprints. Inspired from early works in computer vision, the chroma features are processed by convolving a pre-defined set of 16 binary filters and the extracted structures are used for training the model. The representations derived from the convolution can be stored in a 32 bit inte-

ger. The encoded integer derived from each temporal frame is compressed together into a character representation using Gray codes. The query searching is similar to [7] and is performed in a Hamming space by minimising the bit-rate error (BER) between the candidate and query fingerprint pair. The chromaprint algorithm is implemented by the audio identification service *AcoustID*. It allows fast look-up through API calls to the AcoustID servers. However, the fingerprint is not robust to transformations such as pitch shifting and time stretching. There is an additional issue in this algorithm: the chroma features are computed by pooling STFT or CQT bins to the 12 pitch classes in the Western scale. This also means that the framework should be less robust to atonal music and the kind of music that does not follow pre-defined pitch classes. It must be noted, however, that this notion has not been experimentally tested yet.

Arcas et al [15] proposes a data-driven framework called *Now Playing* which, like [12], is motivated from computer vision. The framework uses a mel-spectrograms of audio recordings to train a convolutional decoder with semi-hard triplet loss. Unlike the previous approaches, *Now Playing* learns latent representations of the spectral features rather than using a pre-defined set of heuristics. The framework is proven to perform real-time query retrieval from a 44 hours long database. *Now Playing* was developed at Google research and [15] provides the details of hardware manifestation of the system along with the neural network-based fingerprinter.

Chang et al [16] has used a similar approach to train the network but, instead of using semi-hard triplet loss, the framework uses contrastive learning as seen in *SimCLR* [17]. The use of contrastive learning significantly reduced the training time of the network and has shown marginal improvements in performance in comparison to the methodology proposed in [15]. The Fig 4 illustrates the general architecture of the above-mentioned neural network fingerprinting frameworks.

1.3 Contributions

The main contributions of this thesis are as follows:

- Implement the state-of-the-art data-driven audio fingerprint framework and

Figure 4: Block diagram representation of the neural network architecture in [15] and [16]

test its performance on a noisy queries and evaluate its robustness to time stretch and pitch-shift. The fingerprint dataset is formed on a sufficiently large music dataset comprising 100,000 songs. This allows us to establish the scalability of the system.

- Study the effect of training the baseline model on pitch-shifted and time-stretched examples. This model is seen to effectively model pitch-shifting while failing at doing so for time-stretching. Nevertheless, it presents important motivations to further analyze the problem.
- Introduce features that are motivated by the domain knowledge of music. We propose two different modifications to the network structure. Both of these are aimed at learning tempo and key invariance for a more robust representation of fingerprints. Following this, we test these frameworks on established performance metrics.

As has been observed so far, the current state-of-the-art in data-driven audio fingerprinting are almost directly borrowed from computer vision technology and is not motivated by domain-specific knowledge of music. This thesis aims to use a data-driven model for learning unique latent representations robust to noise and invariant to musical transformations to an acceptable degree.

Chapter 2

The Baseline Framework

A number of research problems today which deal with textual, visual or multimedia information is impeded by the cost of collecting (or creating) a large-scale accurately labeled data. Despite the popularity of crowd-sourcing platforms which allow many human contributors to be recruited, it is not feasible to expect unbiased and accurate annotations. Recent development in deep learning technology, especially in unsupervised and self-supervised algorithms, have been able to adequately tackle this problem [17][18]. With regard to audio fingerprinting, the central problem can be condensed into to the following idea: creating a compact representation of audio data which uniquely defines the musical aspects of the song. Hence, unsupervised neural network frameworks open up the possibility of learning such representations from the data itself and independent of pre-defined heuristics.

The implementation of the baseline framework is motivated by the success shown by the contrastive learning setting in [16]. Due to the unavailability of a working implementation of the framework in the open-source, the reproduction of the model was a crucial part of this work. Indeed, the experiments performed to learn key and tempo invariance in the following section of this work are built in juxtaposition to the mechanisms used in the baseline framework. Hence, for the sake of completion, to is useful to present the structure and implementation of the same.

The following sections in this chapter deal with the neural network architecture, the

proposed pipeline for data augmentation, validation and testing the framework, and notes on implementation for the purpose of this work.

Figure 5: Spatially separable convolution layers with ReLU activation make up an encoder unit. The block also applies Layer normalisation (LN) between the convolution layers.

2.1 Network Architecture

An audio fingerprint, in the context of this architecture, is a selectively unique¹ low-dimensional embedding of an audio segment. The overall process includes the following steps:

- Compute acoustic features from extracted segments of the audio. A log-scaled mel-spectrogram is derived from each contiguous slice of the audio recording.
- A convolutional encoder to compute high-dimensional embeddings. The encoders consist of spatially separable convolution neural network layers.
- A similarity-preserving deep hashing module to learn the low-dimensional fingerprints. The resultant fingerprints are projected into a L^2 -normalized space to allow nearest-neighbour search, making it suitable for large-scale retrieval.

¹such that noisy representations of the same music segment have a highly similar encoding while being distinct from encodings of other music segments

2.1.1 Encoder

The advantage of dealing with audio in the spectral domain is that it allows network specifications (and the choice of the network itself) to be similar to ones that would be best suited for learning a representation from a visual medium. The segment-level mel-spectrograms are taken as input through a series of encoder units. Each encoder unit consists spatially-separable convolutional layers. Intuitively, this is crucial to the setup as, unlike an image, the axes of the spectrogram represent different features: the spectral and temporal features. In our later experiments we will test the veracity of this intuition. A encoder unit, as can be seen in Fig 5 consists of an array of (a) convolutional layer, (b) layer normalisation, and (c) activation operation.

The network structure is illustrated in Fig 6 and Table 1 gives the detailed specification.

Figure 6: Layer by layer specification of the encoder block. Each convolution unit illustrated here is more accurately the encoder unit (as seen in Figure 5)

2.1.2 Divide-and-Encode Block

The *divide-and-encode* block is deep architecture for supervised hashing. This architecture has been previously implemented unsupervised in triplet-network framework for simultaneous feature learning and hashing of image data [19]. The intermediate representation (embeddings) generated by the encoder module is sliced and fed into a stack of fully-connected layers. Each of the stacked fully-connected layer is hashed into a single hash-bit. The implementation details are illustrated in Fig 7. The output of the divide-and-encode block is normalized into a d -dimensional embedding

space. This vector, which when generated from a pre-trained setting, provides the segment-wise fingerprint of the input audio.

Figure 7: The divide-and-encode module: the vector dimensions shown correspond to the ones used in our work

2.2 SSL Framework

Self-supervised frameworks (such as SimCLR [17]) have been effectively used in transfer learning settings to generate pre-trained embeddings which are suitable for a supervised learning task, such as image classification. This is based on the paradigm that supervised fine-tuning using a small number of unlabeled data on the pre-trained embedding can result in a strong task-specific model [20]. However, one of the crucial modules in such a framework is the self-supervised learning itself and the embedding vectors thus produced, as is observed in our case, can be used for content summarization.

2.2.1 Augmentation Pipeline

The data augmentation as a part of the training pipeline is key to learning robustness while preserving selectivity to false positives. The input to the neural network

Operation Layer		Number of filters	Size of filter, stride	Size of output tensor
Input melspectrogram		-	-	$1 \times 256 \times 32$
Encoder layer (two times)	Convolution	128	$(3 \times 1), (2 \times 1)$	$128 \times 128 \times 32$
	ReLU	-	-	$128 \times 64 \times 32$
	LayerNorm	-	-	$128 \times 64 \times 32$
	Convolution	128	$(1 \times 3), (1 \times 2)$	$128 \times 128 \times 16$
	ReLU	-	-	$128 \times 128 \times 16$
	LayerNorm	-	-	$128 \times 128 \times 16$
Encoder layer (two times)	”	256	”	$256 \times 16 \times 2$
Encoder layer (two times)	”	512	”	$512 \times 4 \times 1$
Encoder layer (two times)	”	1024	”	$1024 \times 1 \times 1$
Divide-&-Encode Block	Split	-	-	$8(\times 128)$
	FC layers	-	-	$1(\times 128)$
	Concat	-	-	128

Table 1: Architecture of the baseline framework: For the sake of brevity, only the first encoder unit has been shown. The Divide-and-Encode block contains splits the feature into 128 partitions and feeds them into FC layers

are a pair of “views” of the same data instance. The difference between the input pairs is that one of them is distorted to simulate real-world discrepancies and transformations. The following are the augmentation steps included in the pipeline:

- *Temporal offset*: This introduces a random time offset of ± 200 ms between the audio segments. The temporal mismatch between the positive data pairs enforces the (query) matching case where there is a significant overlap (more than 80%) between the audio segments.
- *Background noise*: In order to replicate real-world noisy environments, the input audio segments are mixed with ambient noise. The SNR ratio is randomly chosen in the range of 0 to 10 dB. The details about the background noise dataset has been discussed in the next section.
- *Impulse response*: For simulating the reverberation of a closed space (auditorium, classroom, etc), the audio segments are convolved with impulse responses. The details of the dataset itself is discussed in the next section.

Augmentation	Parameter Value	probability
Temporal offset	$\pm 200\text{ms}$	$p_{train} = 1, p_{test} = 0$
Background Noise	SNR=[0,10] dB	$p_{train} = 0.8, p_{test} = 1$
Impulse response	-	$p_{train} = 0.8, p_{test} = 1$
Pitch-shift ³	± 2 semitones	$p_{train} = 0.5, p_{test} = 1$
Time-stretch ³	factor = [0.8,1.2]	$p_{train} = 0.5, p_{test} = 1$
Clipping Distortion	[0,10]%	$p_{train} = 0.8, p_{test} = 0.8$
Time-frequency mask	[10,50]%	$p_{train} = 0.75, p_{test} = 0$

Table 2: Augmentation pipeline: parameters and probabilities

- *Pitch-shift*: One of the proposed way of learning robustness to a certain degree of key changes, is to introduce pitch-shift transformation (pitch-shift factor in the range $\pm 20\%$).
- *Time-stretch*: In the same way, robustness to time-stretching² is central to the interest of this work. The time-stretch factor is randomly chosen in the range $\pm 20\%$.
- *Clipping distortion*: Distort signal by clipping a random percentage of points. The percentage of points that will be clipped is drawn from a uniform distribution between [0-10]%.
- *Time-frequency masking*: Masking a consecutive range of frequency bins and time frames has been observed to increase the robustness of speech modelling [21]. For the purpose of this work, we mask frequency/time bands in the range [10-50]%.

The augmentation process is stochastically applied to one “view” while the other is kept unaltered. In the next subsection we discuss how the augmentation pipeline is utilised to learn the embeddings during the training process. The stochastic parameters for training and querying (testing) is listed in Table 2.

²Unlike time-scaling (which implies slicing or upscaling the time axis), time-stretching implies multiplying the time axis values by a constant factor without changing the spectral content of the sound.

³Both pitch-shift and time-stretch are not implemented on the baseline framework and are instead used in the experimental setup.

2.2.2 Contrastive Learning

The primary idea behind the learning process is to maximise the agreement between differently augmented views of the same data example. The degree of agreement (or disagreement) is decided by the similarity measure. With the final embeddings already in an L^2 -normalized space, the natural choice of similarity measure is cosine similarity. Having established this, let us understand the training pipeline:

- Randomly sample a minibatch containing N data examples. After passing through the stochastic augmentation pipeline, we generate N more distorted *replicas* of the original audio segment. Hence, the resultant batch is essentially $2N$. Let us define, the stochastic augmentation function as $\chi_{\varphi(0,1)}$ which takes in the random parameter φ . So the augmented example s can be defined as $\tilde{s} = \chi_{\varphi}(s)$.
- By definition, the self-supervised setting requires the computation of positive and negative labels. For this work (both the baseline and further experimental models), this is taken care during the parallel augmentation: the *original*, *replica* pair form the positive example. And for each positive pair in the mini-batch, all the other $(N - 1)$ pairs form the negative examples.
- The mini-batch is the input to the encoder function $f(\cdot)$ and the resultant high-dimensional intermediate embeddings are passed through the divide-and-encode block $g(\cdot)$. For each training pair $\{s^{org}, s^{rep}\}$, where

$$s^{rep} = \chi_{\varphi}(s^{org}) \quad (2.1)$$

the final low-dimensional embedding of the mini-batch is given by

$$f \circ g(\{s_k^{org}, s_k^{rep}\}_{k=1}^N) = \{z_k^{org}, z_k^{rep}\}_{k=1}^N \quad (2.2)$$

- The contrastive learning loss is defined on the similarity measure. Given that the vector space is computed through a L^2 -projection, the similarity matrix

can be built based on

$$\text{sim}(z_i, z_j) = z_i^T z_j \quad (2.3)$$

for a pair of data points $(i, j) \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, N\}$.

- The loss function for a pair of data points is given by

$$\mathcal{L}_{(i,j)} = -\log \frac{\exp(\text{sim}(z_i, z_j)/\tau)}{\sum_{k=1}^{2N} \mathbb{1}_{[k \neq i]} \exp(\text{sim}(z_i, z_k)/\tau)} \quad (2.4)$$

where $\mathbb{1}_{[k \neq i]}$ is an indicator function defined as: 1 iff $k \neq i$ and 0 otherwise; τ is the temperature parameter. The final loss is computed across all positive pairs (i, j) and (j, i) in a mini-batch, as the mean of the summation. In essence, this loss function is the negative log probability of classifying the positive sample correctly. The temperature parameter is used for tuning how concentrated the features are in the representation space. For example, when at low temperature, the loss is dominated by the small distances and widely separated representations cannot contribute much and become irrelevant.

The Fig 8 illustrates the contrastive training setup. It must be noted here that in self-supervised tasks, typically [17][20][22], are used in a transfer learning setup where the learnt embeddings are used in a downstream task. In such a case, the utility of the L^2 -normalized space is limited to the training of the contrastive loss and the embedding vector z discarded after training. However, we use the embedding z generated from a trained model as the fingerprint.

The performance of such a contrastive learning framework depends heavily on a large number of negative examples in a mini-batch. Given that the fraction of negative data pair in this example is $(N - 1)/N$, the percentage of negative examples in a batch increases proportionally with batch-size. However, it has been observed [23] that using standard optimizers (Gradient Descent or Momentum), the learning is unstable when batch-sizes are very large. This can be somewhat ameliorated by using memory banks [22]. For the sake of focusing on the problem at hand, we leave this for future work.

Figure 8: The contrastive training mechanism. Positive pair of embedding vectors z are made to “attract” whereas negative pairs are made to “repel”

2.3 Implementation

Digital audio is represented as a sequence of discrete audio samples obtained by sampling and quantization on analog audio signal. However, these discrete samples in time domain can not be used directly in content-based audio analysis. Firstly, the amount of samples is usually huge, which incurs high computational cost. Secondly, the samples are highly correlated, resulting in data redundancy. Thirdly, the information contained in each sample is too small to be meaningful for human perception. Finally, these samples are quite sensitive to distortions, such as channel distortion and background noise. Therefore, it is necessary to extract acoustic features from digital audio in order to manipulate more meaningful information and to facilitate further processing.

Before delving into the training, validation and test settings, it is important to note that they share a common starting point. The input audio segment is pre-processed into overlapping contiguous segments of length 1 second (overlap: 0.5 sec). As a whole, we intend to summarize the content of this audio segment into a fingerprint.

Parameter	Value
Sampling Rate	8000Hz
STFT window function	<i>Hann</i>
STFT window size and hop size	1024, 256
Number of FFT bins	2048
Log-power melspectrogram dimensions	256 × 32
Batch size N	320
Fingerprint dimension d	128
Intermediate embedding dimension h	1024
Learning rate	10^{-4}
Temperature parameter (NTXent Loss) τ	0.1
Number of training epochs	300

Table 3: Table of training parameters

The audio segments are used to generate time-frequency representations (log-power Melspectrogram). It is sampled into a number of points around equally spaced time frames t_i and frequency bins f_j (according to the Mel-frequency scale⁴).

Using an non-linear transformation such as the Mel-scale on the spectral features allows the frequency scale to be more synchronised with the human auditory perception. For the purpose of our later experiments, this also means that the pitch information is linearly-scaled; change in pitch essentially means a linear translation on the frequency axes. This idea has been exploited in our later experiments to study key-invariant models.

2.3.1 Training

The training module comprises a contrastive learning setting on a large music dataset. It is integral that the training module has a chain of stochastic augmentation steps so as to learn robust representations. Table 5 gives details of the size of the dataset. It has been observed that there is no appreciable improvement in performance by increasing the training set from 8000 examples to 10000 examples. As has been discussed earlier, the SSL framework requires a large minibatch with a high percentage of negative examples. This work refers to the findings of [16] for optimal setting of batch-size N and other parameters (refer to Table 3).

⁴ $mel = 2595 * \log_{10}(1 + hertz/700)$

One of the central contributions of this work is exploring the robustness of the fingerprinting framework to pitch-shifting and time-stretching. Hence, there are two different training settings on which the baseline framework is trained. These training modes are distinct by the nature of augmentation pipeline: (a) excluding pitch-shifting and time-stretching transformations, and (b) including pitch-shifting and time-stretching transformations. As is detailed in the following sections, we compare the effect of this distinction on the performance of the models.

The training is performed on a *12-Core AMD Ryzen Threadripper 2920X* processor and two *NVIDIA TITAN XP* GPUs and takes a total time of 7 hours.

2.3.2 Validation

In order to fit the model and fine tune the parameters against a performance metric, the trained model was validated on the GTZAN Genre Classification dataset [24]. The dataset comprises of 1000 audio recordings of 30 second length. The validation step is a three-step process:

- **Creating the fingerprint dataset:** Fingerprints are obtained by freezing the parameters of the trained model and passing contiguous segments (length: 1 sec, overlap: 0.5 sec) of audio through the model. It must be noted that unlike the training module, we discard one of the “views” which is redundant in this module. Also, the fingerprints are obtained from the untransformed audio by passing it through the augmentation pipeline.
- **Creating the query set:** The query set is created from validation set such that it comprises random samples of {1,2,3,5,6,10} second length. Each of these samples are created by transforming the original audio through a chain of noisy transformations⁵.
- **Query searching/matching:** Query searching is performed by an inverted index search on the fingerprint database created from query set. The similar-

⁵The transformations are a subset of the augmentation pipeline and include gain changes, impulse response convolution, background noise mixing and clipping distortion

ity metric for matching is the dot (inner) product of the fingerprint vectors. Intuitively, the query fingerprints are matched against the validation fingerprint database and a “hit” is observed if one of the (query) segments gives the maximum similarity score with a fingerprint belonging to the corresponding song. For the sake, of simplicity, the validation module does not include the segment search strategy employed in the testing module.

The evaluation metric used throughout our experiments is sensitivity rate or the Top-1 hit rate which is given by:

$$sensitivity = \frac{\text{Number of hits in Top-1 search results}}{\text{Sum of hits and misses in Top-1 search results}} \quad (2.5)$$

In contrast to previous findings [16], hyperparameter tuning performed on the validation process shows that the median similarity score of matched queries improves significantly as the temperature parameter τ (refer to Section 2.2 for details) is increased from 0.01 to 0.1. This might be explained by certain differences in the implementation of the algorithm as the Top-1 hit rate is significantly lower than what was reported in [16].

2.3.3 Testing

One of the central motivations behind using a data-driven fingerprinting framework is scalability. Hence, it is important to evaluate the framework against a sufficiently large dataset. The steps involved in the testing module are similar to the validation. We first compute a fingerprint dataset from the pre-trained model, except in this case, we use a test dataset of 100,000 songs (for details, refer to Chapter 3).

Query dataset and fingerprint database is created in a similar manner to the validation process. Ideally, we would like to perform a inverted query search for matching with the dataset. However, an exact search in fingerprint containing approximately 3 million fingerprints is infeasible. Hence, the testing module uses a “product quantization” trick to perform k-nearest neighbour search in the L^2 normalized place. The

Parameter	Value
Number of nearest neighbours, k	4
Number of centroids or prototypes	2^m , $m=8$
FAISS indexing algorithm	IndexIVFPQ
FAISS quantizer	IndexFlatL2
Number of partition clusters to probe, $nprobe$	20

Table 4: Query matching parameters

implication of this enhancement is that the fingerprints are divided into sub-vectors and a large number of clusters (“centroids”) are learnt for each set of sub-vectors. The fingerprints are then symbolically encoded into using these centroids. For the sake of brevity, the overall query search on the encoded vectors is still exhaustive, but the distance score is approximated on the basis of the distance between the centroids. This work does not aim to implement the searching algorithm and instead uses the open source implementation [25] available. Refer to Table 4 for the parameters used for query matching.

As a slight departure from the naive maximum inner product search, the testing module employs a sequence search mechanism which can be summarized as follows:

- k -nearest neighbours are computed for the fingerprint of segment in the query against the fingerprint database.
- The set of indices for consecutive search results $\{Q_k\}_{i=0}^{L-1}$ computed for each query is offset such that for each i

$$\{Q'_k\}_i := \{Q_k\}_i - i$$

where Q_k is the set of k -nearest neighbour indices for each query and L is the number of fingerprints (segments) in the query.

- The set of candidates $C \subseteq \{Q'_k\}_{i=0}^{L-1}$ are such that they are unique elements of the latter.
- Let the set of k -NN distance for $\{Q_k\}_{i=0}^{L-1}$ be $\{D_k\}_{i=0}^{L-1}$. For each segment index

$c \in C$, the similarity score is computed such that $\forall k, i$

$$S_{k,i} = 1 - D_{k,i}$$

$$Score_c = \sum_{Q_{k,i} \in [c, c+L]} S_{k,i}$$

where $S_{k,i}$ is the corresponding similarity result for $Q_{k,i}$.

- The output of the sequence search is the segment index in c with the maximum $Score_c$. A collision may occur when multiple elements of C belong to the same output sequence. This can be resolved by choosing the smallest index.
- Song-level search output is the corresponding song in the database at the index and the output segments are the L consecutive indices starting at the output index.

Throughout the further experiments, performance of the framework is evaluated under two criteria: (a) Sensitivity rate, (b) median similarity score @ top-1 hit. The following chapter elucidates these experiments performed in detail. Unless stated otherwise, the mechanisms and parameter settings used in these experiments are identical to the baseline framework.

Chapter 3

Experimental Setup

As has been established in previous works [16][17], the self-supervised framework trained using contrastive loss is not only a good model for learning visual representations from unlabelled data but it also performs well as a fingerprinting framework. In this chapter, we focus on experiments to evaluate and improve the robustness of the framework to (a) pitch-shifting and (b) time-stretching.

The modifications, introduced into the framework, approach the robustness problem in terms of the musical nature of the data. Intuitively, the model is altered in a way that it can learn a certain degree of key-invariance and/or tempo-invariance. Unlike the methods used in previous fingerprinting frameworks, deep learning architectures do not require explicit feature engineering. Hence, rather than altering the input features fed into the framework, we change the network architecture in order that it can accommodate for such variations.

The following sections give the detail of the dataset used in the experiments, followed by a study of the effect of introducing pitch and time variations into the augmentation pipeline and then propose two substitutes to the shallow convolution layers that can help to learn key and tempo invariance; namely, (a) Scale-invariant convolution layers and (b) Dilated Temporal Convolution layers.

Module	Dataset
Training	10K subset of <code>fma-large</code>
Validation	GTZAN
Testing	{10K, 20K, 25K, 50K, 60K, 100K} subsets of <code>fma-large</code>
Impulse Response	ASH-IR dataset
Background Noise	FSD800 mined from Freesound

Table 5: Datasets used in this work

3.1 Dataset

This work uses a combination of Free Music Archive [26] and GTZAN Genre Classification dataset [24] for the music dataset required for training, validation and testing. At various stages of the work, we use a subset of the `fma-large` dataset which contains $\sim 106,000$ music recordings of 30 seconds length each. The details about the sub-datasets are listed in 5.

In addition to this, the augmentation pipeline requires a background noise and an impulse response dataset. The background noise dataset is compiled for this work by using the Freesound API [27]. For querying the keywords *classroom*, *playground*, *metro* and *bar* were used. The dataset consists of 800 noise audio recordings of lengths 3 to 10 seconds. For impulse response the ASH-IR dataset [28] is used. For training and validation/testing, augmentation datasets are split 8:2 respectively.

3.2 Effect of Augmentation

One of the advantages of using a convolutional encoder is that it is translation invariant, that is, if we translate the patterns on the feature vector, the CNN will still be able to detect the class to which the input belongs. This property is partially utilized by the data augmentation chains to learn translational invariant features in case of the contrastive learning setting.

The convolutional encoder in our baseline framework is fed melspectrograms of audio segments. In spectral features, pitch-shift results in translation along the vertical frequency axis. Hence, key-invariance is equivalent to (or, more precisely, a subset

of) translational invariance. We test this theory by introducing pitch-shifted replicas of the audio as positive examples during the training setting. The resultant model is tested against incrementally pitch-shifted queries¹.

3.3 Scale-Invariant Convolution

Convolutional kernels can learn a robust model which is translation-invariant. However, convolutional neural networks are not naturally invariant to some other transformations such as changes in the scale or rotation of the image. Other mechanisms are required to handle such transformations. Scale-invariant convolutional layers [29] are modules containing convolution layers which aims to “build-in” local scale invariance into the training process.

3.3.1 Tempo Invariance

Before diving into the architecture of the network module itself, it is important to understand that the concept of tempo-invariance in terms of the neural network input features. In the context of our problem, the tempi of two transformations of the same song can occur when different time-stretching factors are applied. Time-stretching (or “shrinking”) implies that the time axis is either scaled up or down while keeping the frequency component unchanged. Hence, scale-invariant neural architecture can be used to learn tempo-invariance.

A similar scale-invariant convolution architecture has been used in downbeat tracking [30] to learn tempi features at different scales and has been reported to be able to learn rhythmic pattern independent of the tempo. In our work, we intend to extend this application to learn latent musical features despite distortions due to timing variations.

Figure 9: (a) A conventional CNN layer vs (b) Scale-invariant convolution module. The figure illustrates a proof of concept by showing only 3 scales. The input and output dimensions of both (a) and (b) are identical

3.3.2 Architecture

A set of convolutional filters are essentially feature detectors; in a single layer, different convolutional kernels detect a particular aspect of a feature vector. Congruently, the goal of a scale-invariant convolution module is to let parallel feature detector respond to patterns at multiple scales.

To do so, the same filters are convolved over multiple resolutions of the feature vector, parallelly. The multiple resolutions are created by upscaling (interpolating) the original feature vector. It must be noted that at each scale the exact same filters are used to convolve the image. Because of the spatial transformation, the parallel convolved feature vectors are at different spatial sizes. Hence, an inverse transformation (downscaling) is applied such that the resultant feature maps are of the same size. Finally the parallel layers are max-pooled into a single output vector which has the same dimensions as the output of a conventional CNN layer. The idea has been illustrated in Figure 9.

¹The pitch-shift factor in this case is limited to ± 2 semitones. This is because we expect our framework to be key-invariant to a certain degree without affecting to false-positive rate in case the query is a version or a cover of the same song.

3.3.3 Memory Allocation

In order to learn the local features invariant of timing variations, we replace the shallow layers of the convolutional encoder (see Section 2.1) of our baseline framework with scale-invariant modules. During implementation it was noted that parallel convolution layers greatly increase the GPU storage requirements. This problem is compounded when there are a series of scale-invariant convolution. One idea was to reduce the batch-size for the training so as to reduce the memory allocation. However, it was observed that the performance of the framework is greatly reduced with the reduction in batch-size. This observation is in line with what has been reported in previous works which simple contrastive learning[17][20].

Since the presence of large number of negative pairs of data examples is so important to learning of the fingerprint representations, one idea would be to use a cross-batch memory queue [31] along with a smaller batch size. This concept has been employed before in learning visual representation using momentum contrast (MoCo)[22]. As a part of this work, we attempted to use a cross-batch memory queue with a simple contrastive setting. However, owing to complications in implementation and lack precedence of the proof of concept, this remains open for future work.

The framework that has been used in this work replaces the first CNN layer in the encoder with a scale-invariant module. However, the results do not show any significant improvement over the baseline model trained (additionally) on time-stretched audio segments.

3.4 Dilated Temporal Convolution

Keeping our focus on temporal invariance learning, convolutional encoders in unsupervised settings have been recently used in music version identification frameworks [32][33] which are able to learn tempo-invariant patterns and structures. Like the scale-invariant module discussed previously, these frameworks aim to increase the receptive field of the convolution kernel and use the size of the receptive field as a parameter to be tuned by the training process. As a result, the model learns the

local temporal context in the latent space. However, there is a slight departure from the architecture employed in our previous experimental setup: instead of rescaling the feature vector, the model uses dilated convolutions to increase the receptive field.

3.4.1 Pyramid of Dilated Kernels

Dilated Temporal Pyramid Convolution

Figure 10: $S^{(1)}$, $S^{(2)}$ and $S^{(3)}$ represent the resultant feature vectors after dilated convolution at dilation rate 1, 2 and three respectively. The concatenated vector J represents the output of the module

Dilated convolutions [34] are a special form of standard convolutions in which the effective receptive field of kernels is increased by inserting zeros (or holes) between each pixel in the convolutional kernel. For a $n \times n$ dilated convolutional kernel with a dilation rate of r , the effective size of the kernel is $[(n - 1)r + 1]$. The dilation rate specifies the number of zeros (or holes) between pixels. However, due to dilation, only $n \times n$ pixels participate in the convolutional operation, reducing the computational cost while increasing the effective kernel size.

Our experimental framework employs parallelly-stacked convolution layers with in-

creasing dilation rates. The resultant feature vectors are concatenated into a single feature vector. Figure 10 conceptualizes the mechanism involved. However, given a melspectrogram as the input vector, scaling across the frequency axis is a redundant operation in the context of our problem as changes in tempo results in variance in scale only across the time axis. Hence, we stacked dilated convolution layers with asymmetrical dilation with rates varying the horizontal axis.

3.4.2 Architecture

While the stacked pyramid convolution scheme is useful to learn a latent feature space invariant of timing variations, we want to introduce key-invariant structures into the mechanism. Hence, let us bring our focus back to convolutional neural networks and translation invariance. In practice, a convolution kernel can be trained to learn local features, on the basis of proximity and patterns, independent of translation. However, most CNN architectures utilize a maxpooling layer, which is a much simpler structure for learning translation invariance.

In pooling operation, we replace the output of the convolutional layers at a certain location with a summary statistic of the nearby outputs (maximum, in case of maxpooling). Hence, even if we change the input slightly, it would not affect the values of most of the pooled outputs. The use of maxpooling can be viewed as adding a strong prior that the function the layer learns must be invariant to translation. When the prior is correct, it can greatly improve the statistical efficiency of the network.

The network architecture of the modified encoder used in this setup has been detailed in Table 6.

Operation Layer		Number of filters	Size of filter, stride	Size of output tensor
Input melspectrogram		-	-	$1 \times 256 \times 32$
DTPCNN Module	Conv [d=1]	128	$(3 \times 1), (2 \times 1)$	$128 \times 256 \times 16$
	Conv [d=2]	128	$(3 \times 1), (2 \times 1)$	$128 \times 256 \times 15$
	Conv [d=3]	128	$(3 \times 1), (2 \times 1)$	$128 \times 256 \times 14$
Concat		-	-	$128 \times 256 \times 45$
ReLU		-	-	$128 \times 256 \times 45$
Maxpooling		128	$(2 \times 1), (2 \times 1)$	$128 \times 128 \times 45$
Encoder layer	Convolution	128	$(3 \times 1), (2 \times 1)$	$128 \times 64 \times 45$
	ReLU	-	-	$128 \times 64 \times 45$
	LayerNorm	-	-	$128 \times 64 \times 45$
	Convolution	128	$(1 \times 3), (1 \times 2)$	$128 \times 64 \times 23$
	ReLU	-	-	$128 \times 64 \times 23$
	LayerNorm	-	-	$128 \times 64 \times 23$
Encoder layer (two times)	”	256	”	$256 \times 32 \times 12$
Maxpooling		256	$(2 \times 1), (2 \times 1)$	$256 \times 16 \times 12$
Encoder layer (two times)	”	512	”	$512 \times 4 \times 3$
Encoder layer	”	1024	”	$1024 \times 1 \times 1$
Divide-&-Encode Block	Split	-	-	$8(\times 128)$
	FC layers	-	-	$1(\times 128)$
Concat		-	-	128

Table 6: Architecture of framework: The input feature vector is fed into the dilated temporal pyramid (DTPCNN) module with dilation rates $\{1,2,3\}$ respectively. Note that the dilation is along the temporal axis (tempo-invariance) whereas the maxpooling operation is along the frequency axis (key-invariance)

Chapter 4

Results

In this chapter, we present the detailed analysis of our findings with respect to the the frameworks that we have elaborated in the previous chapters. For the sake of convenience, we use the following nomenclature while referring to the frameworks:

- *SimCLR-fp*: This refers to the baseline framework employing the convolutional encoder and the SimCLR SSL framework.
- *Aug-SimCLR-fp*: Our baseline framework with trained on pitch-shifted and time-stretched examples as part of the augmented chain ((Section 3.2)).
- *SICnv-fp*: The contrastive learning network with scale-invariant CNN modification (Section 3.3).
- *DTPConv-fp*: The framework with dilated temporal pyramid convolution with maxpooling layers (Section 3.4).

4.1 Scalability

As has been stressed at earlier, scalability to large music datasets is a salient requirement of an audio fingerprinting framework. This is also a motivation of using a data-driven framework. We tested the scalability of our implementation of the

Figure 11: (a) Top-1 hit rate for 10 second audio and (b) Median similarity score vs Size of test dataset

baseline framework by evaluating the performance (sensitivity and median similarity score) on increasing sizes of fingerprint database (Figure 11). It was observed that the the performance of the model is stable up to a certain point and then it falls rapidly. This observation is inconsistent with previous findings [16] which leads us to suspect the efficacy of our implementation.

The rapid fall in performance could be explained by “overcrowding” of the latent embedding space. As has been observed in [35], the temperature parameter τ in the contrastive loss function is a crucial factor involved in the distribution of the fingerprint vectors in the latent space. Smaller values of τ result in more uniform distribution whereas the larger values result in an embedding space where similar vectors are clustered closer together. In order to fine tune the temperature parameter, we trained multiple models with different values of τ . The performance of the models were tested on validation set of size 1000, as has been shown in Figure ??.

As the experimental frameworks are based on slight modifications of the baseline, similar issue with scalability was observed there as well. Hence, the results presented in the following sections are evaluated on a test fingerprint dataset extracted from 25,000 songs beyond which the performance of the model has been observed to deteriorate rapidly.

Figure 12: Value of contrastive loss vs epoch number

	Top-1 hit rate			
Pitch-shift factor	SimCLR-fp	AugSimCLR-fp	SICConv-fp	DTPConv-fp
-3	0.189	0.285	0.240	0.255
-2	0.189	0.442	0.240	0.663
-1	0.192	0.518	0.401	0.670
0	0.820	0.595	0.515	0.750
-1	0.198	0.440	0.376	0.542
2	0.188	0.271	0.210	0.444
3	0.188	0.164	0.210	0.440

Table 7: Top-1 hit rate evaluated on pitch-shifted queries

4.2 Robustness to Pitch-shifting

Except the baseline framework, all other fingerprint databases were additionally trained on pitch-shifted audio segments in the range of ± 2 semitones. Table 7 shows the Top-1 hit rate for a query set of 2000 noisy song¹ segments of 10 seconds length each. The queries have been pitch-shifted by ± 3 semitones.

The baseline model largely fails to learn key-invariant features and underperforms compared to all other models. The *DTPConv-fp* model shows the largest degree of invariance to key changes. It must be noted however, that the model performs sub-optimally with respect to the non-pitch-shifted queries as compared to the baseline

¹The query segments have stochastically transformed using our impulse response and background noise test datasets.

framework. Another promising result shows that the model shows an extent of robustness to pitch-shifts outside the range it has been trained on.

4.3 Robustness to Time-stretching

A similar approach has been employed to evaluate the robustness to time-stretching; the query dataset comprises of 2000 noisy¹ queries (length: 10 second). On this occasion it was observed (Table 8) that the baseline framework significantly performs significantly well against time-stretching as compared to pitch-shifting and the top-1 hit rate is comparable to *Aug-SimCLR-fp*. This is in conflict with our understanding of convolutional networks if were to conclude that the neural encoder in *SimCLR-fp* exhibits tempo-invariant properties. A more plausible explanation could be that the *Aug-SimCLR-fp* model fails to learn tempo-invariant properties and the augmentation chain becomes too “harsh” for the training to take place.

	Top-1 hit rate			
Time-stretch factor	SimCLR-fp	AugSimCLR-fp	SICnv-fp	DTPConv-fp
0.7	0.540	0.422	0.541	0.694
0.8	0.540	0.441	0.545	0.710
0.9	0.691	0.507	0.557	0.724
1.0	0.841	0.611	0.542	0.776
1.1	0.672	0.395	0.589	0.748
1.2	0.600	0.404	0.576	0.750
1.3	0.549	0.388	0.542	0.718

Table 8: Top-1 hit rate evaluated on time-stretched queries

4.4 Size of query

Table 9 shows top-1 hit rate and the median similarity score of the fingerprinting models with respect to the size of the query audio. The queries have been transformed using the augmentation pipeline discussed in Chapter 3. The query matching scheme for this evaluation is a sequence level search (with a error margin of ± 500 ms) as opposed to song-level search used in the previous sections.

It must be noted that the performance of our implementation of the baseline frame-

work (*SimCLR-fp*) is sub-optimal as compared to the results presented in [16]. This might be due to certain unspecified parameter settings and algorithmic structures employed by the authors. The implementation itself being unavailable to us, the results below have been computed after rigorous parameter tuning (details of which can be found in the previous chapters).

It is observed that the performance of the models is somewhat analogous to what was observed in the learning rates of the models as observed in Figure 13. In an ideal setup, the key and tempo invariant models should be comparable in their robustness to query sizes while outperforming *SimCLR-fp* on pitch-shifted and time-stretched queries. In this regard, we observe that *DTPConv-fp* performs at a commensurate rate while still showing sub-optimal hit rates as compared to the baseline.

	Top-1 hit rate			
Query size	SimCLR-fp	AugSimCLR-fp	SIConv-fp	DTPConv-fp
2	0.540	0.251	0.401	0.567
3	0.540	0.313	0.450	0.570
5	0.691	0.481	0.472	0.668
6	0.841	0.522	0.504	0.733
10	0.796	0.590	0.528	0.748

Table 9: Top-1 hit rate vs Query size

Figure 13: Value of contrastive loss vs epoch number

Chapter 5

Discussion

This chapter focuses on a discussion around the salient takeaways from our work. It also presents certain issues and hypothesizes how they may be approached in the scope of future work.

5.1 Conclusion

Audio fingerprinting is a technology to identify some piece of unknown audio in a labeled audio database based on a compact set of features, called audio fingerprint, derived from the signal. It provides reliable and fast means for content-based music information retrieval because audio fingerprints are compact summarizations of the music wave files. A typical audio fingerprinting system contains two major components: fingerprint extraction and query matching. The former extracts and models digital audio signals into concise audio fingerprints which are robust enough to identify unlabeled distorted versions of a song as the same song stored in song database. The latter efficiently looks up the audio fingerprints against the database and judges whether there is a matching song in the database.

This work explores the current state-of-the-art in audio fingerprinting technology and specifically focuses on data-driven frameworks; establishing and implementing a baseline framework which learns compressed representation of music data in an

self-supervised setting. The focus of the work is on robustness of the latent representations learnt by the neural network architecture to noise and transformations. Motivated by the domain knowledge of the characteristics of music (such as the key and the tempo), we introduce modifications into the baseline architecture to create three different models that is theorized to be more robust pitch-shift and time-stretch transformations. The models are tested by evaluating the hit-rate against datasets of distorted and noisy queries.

5.2 Scope for Future Work

This thesis establishes two plausible mechanisms to improve the current state-of-the-art in audio fingerprinting frameworks in the form of these two models: *SICnv-fp* and *DTPConv-fp*. As has been discussed earlier, the former model was observed to have significantly sub-optimal performance despite the fact that the mechanism itself is seen to enforce scale-invariant (and hence, tempo-invariant) learning in previous works. It also faces a reproducibility issue due to excessive memory usage. Incidentally, both these issues could be tackled by some recent developments in SSL and unsupervised learning. Certain frameworks (such as momentum contrast learning) have been seen to benefit in this direction by using a cross-batch memory storage which allows to optimize the memory usage by reducing the size of the mini-batches. By using such a learning mechanism, the alleviated memory can be allocated to deeper scale-invariant convolution layers, thereby, possibly enhancing the tempo-invariance learning property.

Lastly, a problem worth noting is the general sub-optimal performance of the frameworks implemented work. As noted earlier, this problem could be caused by the certain settings that are unavailable in the documentations of the baseline framework invented. However, the modified experimental frameworks show promising results with respect our baseline and so could be posited to behave in a similar fashion when introduced to other (better) implementations of not only the baseline framework but also other ones which employ a similar learning mechanism.

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